

ToolsyBio: A retrieval-augmented generation system for navigating the bioinformatics software landscape

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Abstract—Researchers increasingly rely on free and open-source software (FOSS) for computational analysis across the life sciences. However, the growing volume and diversity of available tools make it difficult to discover, understand, and select appropriate software for specific tasks. We present *ToolsyBio*, a modular system that uses retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) to assist researchers in exploring the bioinformatics software landscape via natural language queries. *ToolsyBio* is built on structured metadata from the *bio.tools* registry and semantically enriched with concepts from *EDAM*, a controlled vocabulary for bioscientific data analysis and data management. The system retrieves relevant tool descriptions using a vector store (*ChromaDB*) and generates grounded responses using a locally served large language model (LLM) via *Ollama*. We describe the system’s architecture, implementation, and potential for improving the findability and usability of bioinformatics tools through a conversational interface.

Index Terms—Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), large language models (LLMs), open source software, FOSS, software discovery, semantic search

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of free and open-source software (FOSS) has transformed bioinformatics research by providing a wide array of tools for data analysis, simulation, and visualization [1]–[4]. However, the sheer volume and diversity of available tools present a significant challenge for researchers—especially those new to a field or seeking solutions for specific, nuanced tasks. Identifying the most appropriate tool, understanding its capabilities and limitations, and evaluating compatibility often requires extensive manual investigation across registries, documentation sites, and publications [5]–[7]. This process is time-consuming and does not always yield the best or most current options.

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Over the past two decades, the rapid growth of bioinformatics FOSS has created a deluge of redundant, overlapping, or under-documented software resources—a phenomenon we call the “Big Tool” problem, in analogy to “Big Data” [8], [9]. These resources are often difficult to search, compare, or assess, leaving researchers and Research Software Engineers (RSEs) increasingly in need of better ways to locate relevant, functional, and trusted tools.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Discovering relevant resources in bioinformatics remains a well-recognized challenge. To address this, several curated and community-driven registries—such as *bio.tools* [10], [11]—have been developed, along with widely adopted annotation ontologies like *EDAM* [12], [13], originally introduced as part of the *EMBRACE Data And Methods* project, to help standardize tool descriptions and metadata. Additional resources, including the NCBI tools list, ELIXIR registries, and other specialized repositories, also contribute to tool discovery. However, many of these require researchers to learn custom interfaces or manually sift through extensive records. Despite their value, such resources are often underutilized and difficult to integrate into routine workflows at scale.

In parallel, a number of tool recommendation systems have been developed to help researchers navigate these complex landscapes. Within the Galaxy platform, recurrent neural network-based models and later transformer-based models have been used to predict workflow extensions and improve tool selection [14], [15]. Other approaches, such as the Bioinformatics Tool Recommendation system (BTR) [16] and provenance-based recommenders for datasets and pipelines [17], have demonstrated the feasibility of learning from usage data to guide tool discovery. While these systems show strong potential within their respective ecosystems, their applicability across the broader bioinformatics software landscape remains limited.

At the same time, advances in natural language processing and the emergence of large language models (LLMs) have opened new possibilities for scientific information retrieval. Retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) architectures enhance LLM responses by grounding them in domain-specific content,

improving factuality and reducing hallucinations [18]. This is particularly relevant for tool discovery, where trust in the response depends on traceable, grounded evidence.

Domain-adapted language models such as BioBERT [19] and SciBERT [20] have demonstrated strong performance on biomedical literature tasks. More recently, RAG-style systems have begun to leverage structured scientific databases to enhance retrieval relevance and factual grounding [21]. Despite these advances, applications of LLM-based retrieval in bioinformatics tool discovery remain limited.

Approaches such as the Galaxy transformer-based recommender [15] and BTR [16] demonstrate the potential of machine learning to suggest relevant tools within structured workflows. *ToolsyBio* extends this concept by supporting flexible natural language queries over a broad set of bioinformatics software.

III. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

Motivated by the challenges of bioinformatics FOSS findability outlined above, *ToolsyBio* operationalizes a RAG framework to enable natural language exploration of tool metadata. *ToolsyBio* is a modular retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) system built using open-source libraries. It consists of four major components: (1) ingestion of tool metadata from *bio.tools*, (2) semantic embedding and indexing via *ChromaDB*¹, (3) prompt-based response generation using a large language model (LLM) served locally through *Ollama*, and (4) a lightweight web-based user interface. The overall architecture is illustrated in Fig. 1.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Data acquisition and preprocessing

The system ingests metadata from the *bio.tools* registry via its REST API endpoint (`bio.tools/api/t`). From the catalog of 30,408 tools, we sampled and exported metadata for 5,795 tools in JSON format. Each record conforms to the *biotoolsSchema* standard [22], providing structured fields such as tool name, description, functionality (annotated with *EDAM* ontology terms [12]), topics, homepage, and documentation links. This metadata was then normalized and flattened into text blocks, forming the input for the embedding and retrieval pipeline.

B. Knowledge base construction (vector store)

To support semantic search, the tool descriptions were chunked and embedded for indexing in a local vector database:

- Text descriptions were first divided into overlapping text chunks of approximately 1,000 characters using LangChain’s *RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter*. This preserves intra-tool context while adhering to model input size limits.
- Each chunk was then encoded into a dense vector embedding using the *all-MiniLM-L6-v2* model from the

¹<https://www.trychroma.com/>

Fig. 1. An overview of the *ToolsyBio* system architecture: A) Describes the workflow steps for data ingestion from *bio.tools*, text chunking and embedding, vector store; B) the order of operations when a user prompts the RAG system; and C) the user interface (UI) layer.

sentence-transformers library [23], chosen for its balance of performance and semantic accuracy.

- The resulting embeddings, along with tool metadata (e.g., tool ID, name, and URL), were stored in *ChromaDB*, a lightweight vector database designed for efficient indexing, storage, and retrieval operations in AI applications. This particular vector store is optimized for top-*k* similarity search.

C. Retrieval and generation

Query resolution in *ToolsyBio* follows a standard RAG pipeline [18], implemented using LangChain² and executed locally via the *Ollama* inference server³.

- 1) The user’s natural language query is embedded using the same *MiniLM* encoder used during indexing.

²<https://www.langchain.com/>

³<https://ollama.com/>

- 2) The resulting vector is used to retrieve the top- k most semantically similar tool description chunks from *ChromaDB* (k typically set to 3–5).
- 3) Retrieved chunks are formatted with source attribution and passed as context to the LLM. The prompt template explicitly instructs the model to generate responses based *only* on this retrieved content, minimizing hallucination.
- 4) The prompt and context are processed by a locally served open-source model (e.g., *Mistral-7B*, *LLaMA3-8B*, etc.) via *Ollama*, ensuring privacy and offline operability.

The generated response is parsed and presented to the user in the front-end interface. While *ToolsyBio* is model-agnostic and compatible with any *Ollama*-supported LLM, the results reported here were produced using *mistral:7b* (ollama.com/library/mistral:7b), pulled in April 2025.

D. User interface

The front-end is built with *Streamlit*⁴, a lightweight Python framework for rapid web app development. Users interact via a conversational text input and receive model-generated responses grounded in retrieved tool metadata. Results include inline references to matched tools, enabling further exploration and verification (Fig. 2). When available, responses include hyperlinks to each tool’s homepage, documentation (e.g., Github or manuals), and a direct link to its *bio.tools* metadata using the format: `bio.tools/api/t/<tool name>?format=json`, where `<tool name>` is the unique tool identifier.

V. RESULTS AND DEMONSTRATIONS

A. Implementation status

The current version of *ToolsyBio* is fully operational. It ingests metadata from the *bio.tools* API, constructs a local vector-based knowledge base, and performs retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) over the subset of 5,795 indexed tools. The core modules—data fetching, chunked embedding, vector storage, LLM integration, and user interface—are implemented in Python. Key scripts include `fetch_biotools.py`, `build_vector_store.py`, and `run_streamlit_app.py`, all of which are documented in the project’s Github repository: <https://github.com/van-truong/toolsybio>.

B. Evaluation setup

We tested *ToolsyBio* using a set of real-world bioinformatics questions designed to assess its ability to retrieve relevant tools and generate coherent, grounded responses. Prompts were drawn from four representative categories: 1) Common analysis tasks (e.g., differential expression); 2) Metadata-based filtering (e.g., input/output formats or interface type); 3) Scenario-based use cases (e.g., viral genome annotation

⁴<https://streamlit.io/>

Fig. 2. *ToolsyBio* interface implemented via *Streamlit*. Users input natural language questions and receive LLM-generated answers grounded in retrieved tool metadata.

workflows); and 4) Ecosystem compatibility (e.g., Python- or R-compatible tools). We then manually reviewed each response to assess:

- The relevance and appropriateness of retrieved tools
- Faithfulness to the source metadata
- Inclusion of useful contextual details (e.g., tool names, capabilities, or links)

C. Representative examples

Example 1: Querying common bioinformatics tasks

Query: “What FOSS tools support differential gene expression analysis?”

Response:

- 1) **THEME** (Homepage: <http://metadb.bmes.nthu.edu.tw/theme/home.php>, Documentation: <http://metadb.bmes.nthu.edu.tw/theme/about.php>) – designed for biologists to identify Differentially Expressed Genes (DEG) from loop-design microarray experiments.
- 2) **PLNseq** (Homepage: <http://homepage.fudan.edu.cn/zhangh/softwares/plnseq/>, Documentation: <https://github.com/zhanghfd/PLNseq/>) – conducts differential expression analysis using high

throughput RNA-seq read count data generated from correlated samples.

- 3) **ideal** (Homepage: <http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/html/ideal.html>, Documentation: <http://bioconductor.org/packages/release/bioc/manuals/ideal/man/ideal.pdf>) – provides functions for an Interactive Differential Expression AnaLysis of RNA-sequencing datasets and offers visualization, validation, and gene-set enrichment analysis.

Analysis: A manual search on the *bio.tools* website returns 397 tools annotated under the “differential gene expression analysis” (DGE) category. Both *THEME* and *ideal* appear in this list, whereas *PLNseq* is tagged under the broader category of “gene expression analysis” and is therefore excluded by stricter filters.

Notably, *PLNseq*’s official description explicitly states that it performs differential expression analysis using RNA-seq data—a core task in transcriptomics. This illustrates how *ToolsyBio* can surface relevant tools that may be missed by conventional index-based filtering. All three tool summaries align with their original metadata and include valid, functional links to documentation, project pages, and *bio.tools* records.

Example 2: Tool discovery by format and interface

Query: “What command-line tools support BAM format for alignment visualization?”

Response: *The command-line tool that supports BAM format for alignment visualization is Bambino* (<https://github.com/NCIP/cgr-bambino>). It is a variant detector and graphical alignment viewer. For more information, refer to the documentation at https://github.com/NCIP/cgr-bambino/blob/master/bambino_jars.tar.

Analysis: *ToolsyBio* is capable of parsing and interpreting multiple semantic constraints within a single user query—for example, combining terms like “command-line,” “BAM format,” and “alignment visualization.” Traditional keyword-based search interfaces often struggle to satisfy such compound queries effectively.

In this case, *ToolsyBio* provides a direct and accurate answer, faithfully paraphrasing the underlying metadata. The provided URLs are valid and functional; however, the *Bambino* GitHub repository has been archived and is now read-only (as of July 8, 2020). This status change is not reflected in the current *bio.tools* metadata and thus falls outside the scope of what the RAG system can incorporate.

Example 3: Use-case driven exploration

Query: “I’m working with viral genomes. What tools can help with gene prediction and clustering?”

Response:

- 1) **Metavisitor:** Allows detection and assembly of viral genomes from deep sequencing data, aiding gene prediction. Homepage: <https://github.com/ARTbio/metavisitor>, Documentation: <https://artbio.github.io/Metavisitor-manual/>.
- 2) **clustermap.js:** A pipeline for generating publication-quality gene cluster comparison figures, supporting sequence clustering and dendrogram visualization. Homepage: <http://github.com/gamcil/clustermap.js>, Related info: <https://bioconductor.org/packages/devel/bioc/html/cluster-map.html>.

Analysis: *ToolsyBio* supports multi-faceted exploratory queries by combining topical and functional metadata. In this example, *Metavisitor* closely matches the user’s intent, addressing both “viral genomes” and “gene prediction.” While *clustermap.js* does not explicitly reference viral contexts, it is a relevant and practical tool for gene clustering and visualization tasks. This response demonstrates the system’s ability to surface tools based on functional alignment, even when exact keyword matches are absent.

Example 4: Meta-reasoning and workflow component identification

Query: “Find tools for visualization that integrate with Python or R.”

Response:

- 1) **PyVisualFields** (Python) – A package for Visual Field Analysis, providing functions for regression, visualization, standardization, and normalization. <https://github.com/mohaEs/PyVisualField> (Homepage), <https://pyvisualfields.readthedocs.io/> (Documentation).
- 2) **VisualLife** (Python) – A library for interactive biological data visualization in rich web applications, useful for displaying protein and DNA sequences. <https://bitbucket.org/dgront/visualife/> (Homepage), <https://visualife.readthedocs.io/> (Documentation).
- 3) **GOplot** (R) – An R package enabling multilayered visualizations for functional analysis data, with a focus on expression data. <https://wencke.github.io/> (Homepage), <https://wencke.github.io/> (Documentation).

Analysis: This example illustrates *ToolsyBio*’s ability to match tools not only by functionality (visualization), but also by programming environment compatibility (Python or R). The system successfully surfaces tools from both ecosystems—*PyVisualFields* and *VisualLife* for Python, and *GOplot* for R—demonstrating an awareness of platform-specific usage contexts.

However, the query itself is broad and underspecified. The returned tools span different biological domains (e.g., visual field analysis, molecular sequence visualization, and functional enrichment), which may not all be equally relevant to a given use case. While the results are technically accurate, this example highlights the importance of precise querying for task-specific recommendations

(e.g., “genome visualization in R” or “heatmap plotting in Python”).

Overall, the example shows that *ToolsyBio* can interpret abstract, high-level prompts and retrieve tools across different software ecosystems, but refinement of the query would improve the interpretability and usefulness of the output.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Principal findings

ToolsyBio demonstrates the feasibility of applying a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) framework to support natural language exploration of bioinformatics software resources. By grounding model responses in structured metadata from *bio.tools* [10], [11] and semantically enriched *EDAM* ontology terms [12], [13], the system delivers context-aware, traceable answers aligned with researcher intent. The integration of open-source infrastructure, such as *ChromaDB*, *LangChain*, and *Ollama*, enables fully local, privacy-preserving deployment, user-driven customization, and reduces barriers to adoption in biomedical research environments. Our evaluation indicates that *ToolsyBio* can effectively retrieve and explain relevant tools across a wide variety of query types, including functional tasks, metadata-based filtering, and use-case-driven discovery.

B. Limitations and opportunities

While *ToolsyBio* offers a promising approach to tool discovery, several limitations highlight opportunities for future enhancement:

- 1) **Knowledge sampling and registry limitations** — The current implementation uses a sampled subset of 5,795 tools from the full *bio.tools* catalog (30,000+ tools). This improves tractability but may limit coverage, especially for newer or niche tools not yet registered. Community-driven registries depend on proactive user participation and may lag behind ecosystem growth.
- 2) **External source integration** — The system draws exclusively from *bio.tools*. Expanding to additional registries (e.g., *FAIRsharing* [24], NCBI tools), extracting from live webpages, publication or source code repositories, and structured documentation would enable broader, deeper discovery across life sciences domains. Over-reliance on a single registry may also risk future obsolescence, as seen with the now-defunct *OmicTools* [9].
- 3) **Metadata depth and expressiveness** — Many tool entries lack important fields such as code usage examples, supported formats, or comparative features. Enriching records with curated documentation, evaluations, or user-contributed metadata [25] could improve the quality of responses.
- 4) **Static top- k retrieval** — The current top- k (typically $k = 3$ or $k = 5$) retrieval model may not always align

with user intent. Some scenarios call for a single best-fit tool, while others require a broader set. Supporting dynamic control over the number and ranking of results would enhance flexibility. Additionally, combining semantic and keyword search, re-ranking strategies, or adaptive filtering could improve precision—especially for ambiguous or multi-hop queries.

- 5) **Reasoning complexity** — Tasks involving comparison or multi-step reasoning (e.g., “Which tool is better for X task given Y data and Z constraints?”) remain difficult due to limited metadata granularity and model inference limits. Ontology-guided disambiguation and structured reasoning chains are promising directions.
- 6) **Evaluation framework** — A more formal evaluation pipeline is needed to assess system performance comprehensively, including gathering additional feedback from expert bioinformaticians and conducting failure mode analyses. For example, Q&A prompts could be retrieved from benchmark datasets (e.g., *BioASQ* [26]) and re-framed for tool-usage inquiries rather than biomedical facts.
- 7) **Refresh and extensibility** — Regular re-indexing, faceted filtering, and query history would improve usability over time. Future versions could integrate hosted LLMs or evolve into agent-based frameworks (e.g., *BioChatter* [27]) with task-specific modules.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, *ToolsyBio* presents a retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) system for discovering and understanding bioinformatics software resources. By grounding large language model outputs in curated metadata from *bio.tools*—structured using *biotoolsSchema* and enriched with *EDAM* ontology concepts—the system delivers transparent, context-aware responses to natural language queries. Our initial evaluation demonstrates that RAG-based methods, when supported by structured, high-quality metadata, can effectively assist in tool discovery workflows that are interpretable, extensible, and usable by both research software engineers (RSEs) and domain researchers.

Looking ahead, we aim to extend *ToolsyBio* in several promising directions. First, we are considering expanding the current set of [four] real-world bioinformatics questions into a larger benchmark as a potential community resource for evaluating similar RAG applications in the future. Secondly, we aim to explore how this approach could be enhanced through agentic AI workflows, e.g. experimenting with the reasoning capabilities of LLMs, generating example code for tool suggestions, Model Context Protocol (MCP)⁵ servers, ontology-guided reasoning, multi-source knowledge integration, tool-chaining, and more interactive conversational capabilities. If successful, these enhancements could position RAG-based tool search systems as a practical research companion

⁵<https://modelcontextprotocol.io/docs/getting-started/intro>

for navigating the expanding and evolving FOSS landscape in bioinformatics.

CODE AVAILABILITY

The source code, documentation, and example datasets are publicly available at: <https://github.com/van-truong/toolsybio>.

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